

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Insights of Research Scholars towards Research Culture in Teacher Education Institution

Sonu Bara * and Sangeeta Chauhan

Department of Education, Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University (A Central University), Vidya Vihar, Raebareli Road, Lucknow- 226025 (U.P), India.

International Journal of Science and Research Archive, 2025, 17(03), 1052-1059

Publication history: Received 06 November 2025; revised on 12 December 2025; accepted on 15 December 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/ijrsra.2025.17.3.3262>

Abstract

The research paper “Insights of Research Scholars towards Research Culture in Teacher Education Institution” investigates the insight and experiences of doctoral research scholars with the research culture in Department of Education NACC A++ Graded state Universities. Research culture is a multidimensional concept that involves the value of the institution, academic norms, research practices, relationships between the scholar and supervisor, infrastructural support and collaboration and innovation opportunities. Financial constraints, bureaucracy, plenty of unsystematic mentoring, and lack of sufficient research facilities usually affect the academic advancement and the experience of research overall in a number of state universities. The paper is set to examine the views of scholars towards the usefulness of research support systems, accessibility of academic materials, research funding accessibility, research climate at the departmental level, and institutional policies that influence scholarly output. Based on a qualitative method a semi-structured interview and thematic analysis were used to obtain the data and identify the common patterns in the experience of scholars. The findings point out not only the strengths, such as intellectual freedom, favourable peer networks, and increasing attention to the visibility of research, but also the challenges, such as infrastructural gaps, lack of interdisciplinary exposure, excessive teaching volume on the faculty, and lack of institutional acknowledgement of research successes. The research highlights the importance of intensifying research environment in state universities in terms of funding, capacity-building programmes, enrichment of supervisory practices, and establishment of collaborative platforms. This paper learned by the views of scholars can inform policy makers, academic leadership, and institutions to come up with strategies that can help to create a more vibrant, inclusive, and sustainable research culture. Finally, research culture needs to be improved in order to improve the quality of higher education and develop research output in the country.

Keywords: Research Culture; Academic Environment; Higher Education

1. Introduction

Research culture is the collective values, attitudes, norms, and practices that characterise the research culture of an institution (The Royal Society, 2024). For higher education, especially in state universities, research culture plays a crucial role in the quality, productivity, and innovation of scholarship (Pratt et al., 1999). State universities in India are major pillars of the national education system and make significant contributions to knowledge production and socio-economic growth (University Grants Commission, 2008). But their ability to cultivate an active research culture is often tested by meagre funding, infrastructural limitations, bureaucratic obstacles, and differences in faculty commitment and institutional leadership (Billot, 2010; McRoy et al., 2012). Knowledge of research scholars' views provides in-depth understanding of the lived experiences of individuals who directly participate in research endeavours (Merriam, 2015). These views influence not only the manner in which research is carried out but also how novice scholars manage institutional frameworks, mentoring relationships, and scholarly expectations (Marchant, 2009). A variety of factors influence such views, such as

* Corresponding author: Sonu Bara

availability of resources, supervisor support, departmental atmosphere, peer collaboration, ethical conduct, access to publication channels, and appreciation of research contributions (Hill & Haigh, 2011). Current policy actions like the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 emphasise more research output and a robust research ecosystem in universities (Ministry of Education, 2020). However, it is crucial to implement such reforms with an understanding of the ground realities, particularly from the research scholar's point of view, who are the future academic brains (White & Deevy, 2020). Investigating this theme is essential for determining gaps and strengths in current practices and for proposing evidence-based interventions to enhance the research environment (Rossouw & Niemczyk, 2019). It also offers a forum for assessing institutional strategies, administrative policies, and support systems that shape the scholarly experience (Altbach & Salmi, 2011). By concentrating on state universities, the study accentuates the singular challenges and opportunities inherent in public institutions, which tend to serve diverse and underrepresented student populations (Singh, 2017).

This survey of research scholars' insight can also serve as a reference guide for institutional reforms, policy-making, and capacity-building initiatives. This study can help shape a strong research culture aligned with national and international academic standards (World Economic Forum, 2018; Sustainable Development Goal 4, 2023). Research is a vital pillar of higher education, serving as a driving force for knowledge creation, innovation, and societal progress (William & Michael, 2018). In the Indian higher education context, state universities account for the bulk of the research population. These institutions often face challenges in nurturing a strong and sustainable research culture due to constraints such as limited funding, lack of infrastructure, inadequate guidance, and administrative inefficiencies (University Grants Commission Report, 2019). Research culture refers to the collective norms, values, practices, and support systems within an institution that foster research engagement, academic exploration, and innovation (The Royal Society, 2023).

Current national policies such as the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 and reports of the University Grants Commission (UGC) have emphasised the need to enhance research quality and encourage innovation across all higher education institutions (Ministry of Education, 2020; University Grants Commission, 2008). The National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) also includes research, innovation, and extension as a key criterion for institutional accreditation (Singh, 2017). These developments highlight the urgency of assessing the actual conditions of research culture in state-run universities, which often struggle to match the research intensity of central or private institutions (Dambo, 2016). Research scholars are in a unique position to reflect on the quality and nature of the research environment in their institutions. Their insight can highlight not only the strengths of the system but also the structural deficiencies that impede meaningful research outcomes (Pratt et al., 1999; Rossouw & Niemczyk, 2019). Exploring their views provides valuable insights about institutional practices, faculty support, availability of resources, opportunities for academic growth, and the overall environment for research and innovation (Hill & Haigh, 2011). Therefore, the aim of this study is to explore the insight of research scholars about the research culture in state universities. It seeks to understand the extent to which these institutions are able to foster a conducive research environment and support scholarly development (Altbach & Salmi, 2011). The findings of this research can contribute to policy-making, improving institutional practices, and the broader goal of strengthening the research ecosystem in Indian higher education (Jain, 2019; White & Deevy, 2020).

1.1. Statement of the Problem

Despite various reforms and initiatives to promote research in higher education, state universities often face challenges in developing a strong research culture. Researchers, being the focus of academic exploration, face obstacles such as limited resources, inadequate guidance, bureaucratic delays, and lack of institutional support. These factors can hinder their research productivity and overall academic development. Although policies such as NEP 2020 and UGC guidelines emphasize quality research and innovation, the ground reality in many state universities is still unclear. This study seeks to explore the insight of researchers to assess the current research environment and identify factors influencing research culture in state universities. Hence, the researcher selected the topic "Insight of Research Scholars towards Research Culture in Teacher Education Institution"

1.2. Rationale of the study

Research culture is very important in determining the quality, productivity, and overall academic environment of higher education institutions (Altbach & Salmi, 2011; Billot, 2010). In state universities, where various cohorts of research scholars undertake advanced studies, it is important to understand their insight to assess the effectiveness of current research practices and identify areas for improvement (Hill & Haigh, 2011; White & Deevy, 2020). Though basic academic structures exist, most state universities face challenges concerning infrastructure, supervisory support, peer collaboration, and institutional policies (McRoy et al., 2012; Rossouw & Niemczyk, 2019). These aspects have a direct impact on scholars' motivation, research productivity, and academic development (Jain, 2019; Pratt et al., 1999).

Studying the insight of research scholars is useful for understanding how they experience the research environment, what obstacles they face, and which forms of support they consider most significant (Merriam, 2015; Dambo, 2016). Such insights

are necessary to enhance research culture, improve institutional effectiveness, and advance the general quality of higher education (NEP 2020; The Royal Society, 2024). Thus, the proposed research aims to explore scholars' opinions to inform policymaking and facilitate a more dynamic and supportive research environment within state universities (University Grants Commission, 2019).

1.3. Significance of the study

This research is valuable since it aims at learning how research scholars perceive the culture of research in state universities, which are leading institutions in the development of academic and scientific achievements in the country (Altbach & Salmi, 2011). The research offers critical information on weaknesses and strengths of the current research environment by looking at the experiences of scholars (Merriam, 2015). It brings up the main problems associated with infrastructure, supervisory support, institutional practices, and collaborative opportunities that have direct impacts on the quality and productivity of research (Billot, 2010; McRoy et al., 2012; White & Deevy, 2020).

The results of this research can help university administrators, policymakers, and academic leaders develop more effective strategies to enhance research ecosystems (Pratt et al., 1999; Rossouw & Niemczyk, 2019). It may be used to strengthen systems of institutional support, enrich research centres, and create a more collaborative and thought-provoking atmosphere (Hill & Haigh, 2011). Also, the research contributes to the current body of knowledge on research practices in higher education, providing a foundation upon which future studies can be conducted (Jain, 2019; University Grants Commission, 2008). Finally, it will strive to increase the research performance of institutions and foster a sustainable and dynamic research culture within state universities (The Royal Society, 2024).

1.4. Review of Related Literature

Researchers reviewed various theses, research articles, research papers and journals with reference to the current studies in the research culture. Related literature helps to know about the previous research works done in the area of present study. Many studies have been done on research culture and teacher education, but so far research papers, articles, and journals related to research culture have been received which are as follows:- **Shamai, S., & Drora, K. (2002)** studied on the topic "Research Activity and Research Culture in Academic Teachers' Colleges in Israel". This paper discusses the importance of research activity of academic teachers in Israeli colleges and analyses how this activity is conducted. The aim of this paper was to examine the contribution of research to professional staff development and the status of research activities in teacher training colleges. This paper was based on a theoretical and practical framework. The researcher pointed out the major barriers hindering research in colleges and the conditions affecting research performance were indicated. Analyzed the character of actual research activity and focuses on research committees and research units, which are central organizational tools for research development by analyzing and describing the range of research culture in colleges: from absent to optimal. The paper contributes a theoretical and practical framework and can support the advancement and development of research activity in the colleges. **Pratt, M., M. Dimitri, & David, C. (2006)** studied on the topic "Developing a Research Culture in University Faculty". In this study, researchers applied a case study and used quantitative methods. The objectives of this study are the perception of academic staff on teaching organization research culture in Indian higher education institutions. Samples were taken for data collection in 20 higher education institutions; the researchers used a non-probability purposive sampling technique for data collection by constructing a closed questionnaire with 60 items. Data were analyzed by using Likert scale and Bartlett test. The researchers found positive results on the perception of teaching-learning and research culture among academic staff in teacher education institutions in higher education. **Rawat, K. J. (2012)** Studied on the topic "Research Culture in Teacher Education: A Study of Insight of University Teacher Educators in Pakistan". In this study researcher applied a mixed method by using an explanatory research approach to prepare a detailed understanding of the research culture to encourage culture research in teacher education institutions of Pakistan. The objectives of this study were to explore the reasons for the pathetic condition of research in the field of education through the perspective of teacher educators. For data collection, five Pakistani universities were selected; in-depth interviews were conducted with 10 teacher educators. The interview was conducted to collect the data; in-depth interviews were conducted with ten teacher educators from five different Pakistani Universities. Thematic analysis was used to analyse the data which are obtained from the interviews. The researcher found that research scholars are not more interested do to their research in well-mannered and systematic and they want to complete their research in a very short time they are not interested do to their research in depth but most of the teachers want to award doctorate degree for their academic and professional enhancement, and the findings also revealed that research plays an important role for developing and enhancing the research culture. **Muller, A. (2014)** studied on the topic "Promoting a Research Culture and Scholarship at a Higher Education Institution" the researcher tried to analyzed the situation of higher education institutions in reference to research culture in South Africa. This article was based on qualitative research. The researcher has concluded that there is a need to focus on multidimensional and holistic approach to maintain research culture in higher education institutions so that the academic staff in the field of education can do scholarly work and create a positive environment of research culture. **Ponnuswamy, I., & Manohar, Hansa, L. (2014)** studied on the topic "Impact of

Learning Organization Culture on Performance in Higher Education Institutions". The purpose of this article was to investigate and study the perception of research culture among academic members to know about the organizational culture in Indian higher education institutions. This article was based on quantitative research. The sample was selected through non-probability purposive sampling technique. The Researchers collected data based on Researchers collected data on pen-paper based on questions with 43 items. Data were analyzed by using Likert Scale and Bartlett test. The researcher concluded that the culture of organizations plays an important role in inquiry and perception based learning in various dimensions in higher education institutions. And organizational culture plays a very important role in fostering Newark for the cultural environment of higher education institutions, for team learning, for communication between institutions, and for improving research. Olvido, M. M. (2015) Studied on the topic "Development of Research Cultures in Teacher Education Institutions: gestation-expansion-maturation Theory". He developed the theories of research culture on the basis of three dimensions- gestation, expansion and maturation. The researcher Collected reviews related to research culture as a secondary source for data collection. Researcher found that the meaning of research culture needs to be defined in a number of contexts. Researcher also discussed that how 'research culture' can be developed in teacher education institutions and how the research culture is currently needed to maintain, develop, and progress the quality of research. William, G. T., & Michael, L. (2018) studied on the topic "Institutional Culture in Higher Education" .the purpose of this article was to understand the culture of institutions and study on various dimensions to improve it. This article was based on qualitative research. The researcher concluded that it is important to develop cultural values in colleges and universities in higher education and encourage researchers to develop the culture of the institutions and thereby help in developing the culture of the institutions successfully. White, P. J., & Deevy, C. (2020) studied on the topic "Designing an Interdisciplinary Research Culture in Higher Education: A Case Study". The purpose of this article was to develop research culture in higher education institutions through interdisciplinary approach. This article was based on qualitative research. The case study was adopted by the researchers. This article concluded that research in higher education institutions is a continuous process. It helps to enhance the discipline in an inclusive creative way, by communicating with interdisciplinary dimensions and increasing interest and awareness in interdisciplinary research culture. Rossouw, J.P. (2020) studied on the topic "Developing a Faculty Research Culture in Higher Education: A South African Perspective". The purpose of this paper is to examine how academic managers can improve the prevalent weak or mediocre research culture and the role of managers and academics in driving innovation in research. This paper was based on qualitative research. It was concluded by the researcher that while reviewing the scholars, it was found that negative results have been obtained. But with a positive approach, research can be transformed into a vibrant environment characterized by innovation and productivity. Jayachandran, J., & Chandrasenan, D. (2021) studied on the topic "Institutional Research Culture Scale (IRCS): Development and Validation in the context of Universities in Kerala, India" the purpose of this article was to improve, enhance and develop the attitudes, beliefs, expectations, attitudes, and norms of researchers and research students towards research culture in higher institutions of Kerala. This article was based on quantitative research. The sample was selected through multistage cluster sampling technique. The Researchers collected data based on a normative survey and the Likert Scale. The researchers concluded that promoting research productivity in higher education institutions, research environment, developing research culture and research capability among researchers and faculty members are the keys to the quality of research in the department.

1.5. Research Questions

- How do research scholars describe their experiences and insight of the current research culture in Education Department of NACC A++ state universities?
- What factors do research scholars identify as supporting or limiting the development of a strong research culture within state universities?

1.6. Research Objectives

- To explore research scholars' insight on the existing research culture in Education Department of NACC A++ state universities of Uttar Pradesh.
- To identify the key factors that facilitate or hinder the development of a strong research culture in Education Department of NACC A++ state universities of Uttar Pradesh from the perspective of research scholars.

2. Research Methodology

2.1. Research Method

The researcher used a Qualitative method to explore the insights of research culture.

2.2. Research Design

Phenomenological design has been employed. As the purpose of the research is to understand the experiences of Research scholars who are currently enrolled in 2nd and 3rd year the Ph.D. program in the Teacher Education Department in NACC A++ Graded state Universities of U.P

2.3. Population of the Study

The present study population comprises of Teacher Education Department of NACC A++ Graded State Universities of Uttar Pradesh

2.4. Sample size

The present study comprised 08 research scholars of Department of Teacher Education from 02 state universities Graded as NACC A++ who are enrolled in Ph.D. programme before 2024, located in eastern part of Uttar Pradesh.

2.5. Sampling Technique

Convenience sampling approach has been used by the researcher to gain access to available willing researcher scholars in order to ensure feasibility and in-depth insight essential for the phenomenological study.

2.6. Tools of the Study

The researcher has developed a tool, "Semi-Structured Interview Schedule for Research scholars (SSIRS)".

2.7. Data Collection Process

The researcher adopted a semi-structured interview schedule as the method of data collection.

2.8. Data Analysis

The researcher has used a semi-structured interview schedule with 8 research scholars who had spent 2-3 years at the university. Keeping in mind the objectives of the research, the researcher divided the interview schedule into 4 dimensions and prepared an interview schedule, which included questions related to research environment, institutional infrastructure, departmental support, personal experience, resulting in a total of 12 questions.

After conducting the interviews, the researcher analysed the researchers' responses to all the questions for qualitative analysis, which were analysed as follows:

Table 1 Themes wise table representing question distribution

S. No.	Themes	Questions No.
1	Research Environment	1-3
2	Institutional Infrastructure	4-5
3	Departmental Support	6-8
4	Personal Opinion	9-12

In this table, themes have been extracted based on the interviews, which have been analysed below based on the themes, which are as follows:

2.8.1. Theme 1: Research Environment

The research environment appears mixed, balancing supportive supervision with limited peer interaction. Researchers expressed confidence when presenting to their supervisors, as one noted, "I feel confident when I present my ideas in front of my supervisor." However, hesitation persists regarding peer discussions: "I feel hesitant to discuss research openly with fellow researchers." This aligns with Brew (2001), who argues that active peer dialogue is crucial for building a vibrant research culture. Although researchers are open to collaboration, the absence of regular and structured interactions limits opportunities for deeper intellectual exchange. Thus, while supervisory communication is strong, the broader research environment lacks the interactive components essential for fostering collaborative scholarship.

2.8.2. Theme 2: Institutional Infrastructure

Respondents acknowledged the presence of basic facilities such as library and computer labs. One researcher affirmed, "Facilities like library are available in the department, which makes work easier." Yet, they also reported inadequate functionality and limited research resources, stating, "The library does not work properly and there is a shortage of research books." High-quality research infrastructure directly influences the rigor and productivity of academic work. While the institute has foundational infrastructure, its limited functionality and scarcity of specialised resources hinder researchers' ability to engage in advanced research. Strengthening infrastructural quality is therefore essential for improving research output.

2.8.3. Theme 3: Departmental Support

Departmental support is present but irregular. Researchers found periodic seminars and lectures useful; one shared, "Seminars and lectures give us new ideas." However, the irregular frequency weakens their long-term impact, as another respondent observed: "Since the programs are not regular, they do not lead to long-term improvement in research skills." This aligns with Ramsden (2003), who suggests that regular academic engagement opportunities enhance scholarly competence and research culture. The department appears more focused on formal procedures (DRC, RAC) than sustained intellectual enrichment. Strengthening continuity and creating structured academic platforms would significantly boost research capacity.

2.8.4. Theme 4: Personal Opinions

In personal reflections, researchers appreciated administrative support, particularly for fellowships: "The staff is very helpful in matters related to fellowships." However, academic engagement suffers because faculty members are often busy in some administrative responsibilities. Peer communication occurs but lacks academic depth, and departmental meetings focus heavily on administrative matters. This reflects findings by Altbach and Salmi (2011) who notes that research environments in many institutions remain administratively driven rather than academically driven. Consequently, opportunities for intellectual dialogue are limited, though researchers remain hopeful about improvements in academic engagement.

2.9. Overall Analysis

The overall research culture at the institute combines positive practices and serious challenges regarding different themes. On the positive side, researchers feel a certain degree of comfort and confidence while relating to their supervisors, meaning there is a foundational level of academic support (Hill & Haigh, 2011). Occasional participation in seminars, conferences, and workshops also contributes to exposure and intellectual growth (Marchant, 2009). Expert lectures and academic events are organized from time to time within the department, which help to provide a platform for idea exchange (White & Deevy, 2020). The institutional atmosphere is judged socially, academically, and economically as supportive to a moderate extent, with encouragement toward interdisciplinary research (Altbach & Salmi, 2011; Ministry of Education, 2020). Cooperation from non-teaching staff and partial access to departmental facilities further strengthen the academic atmosphere (The Royal Society, 2024).

However, several negative features weaken this research culture considerably. The greatest concern is the low level of interaction among peers and a lack of regular, meaningful discussion among researchers, which naturally limits collaborative learning and idea development (Pratt et al., 1999). Institutional infrastructure does exist, although it is insufficient in quality, with non-functional labs, poor resources in the library, and a reliance on online material hindering good research progress (McRoy et al., 2012). Supervisory support is available, though not consistently, due to time constraints, affecting continuity and depth (Billot, 2010). Departmental initiatives are mainly formal and not frequent enough to build up sustained research capacity (Rossouw & Niemczyk, 2019). Opportunities for hands-on research, project work, and publication support are very few, which means limited practical exposure and academic output (Jain, 2019).

While partially positive, institutional culture is undermined by irregularity and a lack of seriousness; administrative priorities override research discussions (William & Michael, 2018). Further constraints in this research environment are difficulties in obtaining fellowships, limited availability of faculty members, and a lack of focused communication (University Grants Commission, 2019). Thus, while the institute has shown promise through its supportive elements and basic structures, improvements in the areas of infrastructure, supervisory engagement, and departmental and collaborative opportunities are very much needed in order to foster a strong and alive research culture (Singh, 2017; Sustainable Development Goal 4, 2023).

The findings of this paper reveal that we are not able to develop a healthy environment in the department which would prove useful for the researchers, and the environment of the department is not developed in such a way that group

discussions can be held from the research point of view. The department does not provide researchers with the kind of support they need to focus on the quality and originality of their research. Within the department, researchers receive guidance and support from their mentors. While departmental support is provided, researchers are required to work on their own. The research culture of the institutions is general, but concrete steps are taken from time to time to improve this culture, which can help develop a good research culture. Thus, the interviews revealed that the state's institutions have a strong research culture, but shortcomings need to be addressed, such as increasing resources, providing appropriate guidance for publications, promoting community gatherings, increasing participation in research activities, and periodically reviewing research strategies. Adoption etc. This will promote research culture in the state institutions, along with enhancing the quality of research and high level productivity.

3. Conclusion

This paper demonstrates that the research culture of the institute has its advantages and significant weaknesses. Scholars can freely interact with supervisors and acquire certain exposure in seminars and lectures by experts (Hill & Haigh, 2011). Nevertheless, the absence of strong peer contact, substandard infrastructure, inconsistent supervisory attention, and insufficient publication and actual research opportunities greatly slow the process (Billot, 2010; McRoy et al., 2012). The activities in the department are substantially formal, and the administrative priorities tend to dominate the research discussions (Altbach & Salmi, 2011). Research growth is also hampered by other challenges, like the inability to develop fellowships and a lack of faculty (University Grants Commission, 2019). In a nutshell, there should be massive enhancements to make the research ecosystem robust.

Through this paper, the researcher has tried to understand how thinking culture can be developed in teacher education institutions and how the researchers of the department play their role in maintaining that culture. For this, the researcher organized an interview to understand the activities and efforts through which research culture can be created and developed in the department with available resources (Merriam, 2015). Along with this, the paper identifies the steps that should be taken to strengthen research culture and the shortcomings that must be addressed. The paper also highlights that improving infrastructure, maintaining, fostering opportunities for collaboration, and focusing on research-focused practices all play key roles in maintaining a strong and sustainable research culture.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] Altbach, P. G., & Salmi, J. (Eds.). (2011). The road to academic excellence: The making of world-class research universities. World Bank Publications.
- [2] Billot, J. (2010). The changing research context: implications for leadership. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 33(1), 37-46.
- [3] Brew, A. (2001). Conceptions of research: A phenomenographic study. *Studies in higher education*, 26(3), 271-285.
- [4] Dambo, N. (2016). An Ethnographic study of the culture of twelfth grade upward students in the Midwest. Electronic thesis and Dissertation, 2004-2019. <https://stare.library.UCF.edu/etd/5072>
- [5] Hill, M. F. & Haigh, M. A. (2011). Creating a culture of research in teacher education: learning research within communities of practice, *Studies in Higher Education*. 37(8), 971-988.
- [6] Marchant, T. (2009). Professional Doctorate Research in Australia: Commentary and Case Studies from Business, Education and Indigenous Studies. Griffith Research Online. Accessed On (3 August 2023). <http://dps.scu.edu.au/index.php/9/>
- [7] McRoy, R. G., Flanzer, J. P. & Zlotnik, J. L. (2012). Building Research Capacity and Infrastructure. New York: Oxford University Press.
- [8] Merriam, S. (2015). *Qualitative Research: a guide to design and implementation* (4th Ed.). Jossey-Bass, U.S. ISBN-9781119003601

- [9] Ministry of Education. (2020). National Education Policy 2020. Government of India. chrome-extension://efaidnbmninnibpcjpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/NEP_Final_English_0.pdf
- [10] Pratt, M, Margaritis, D & Coy, D (1999), Developing a research culture in a university faculty. Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 43-55.
- [11] Ramsden, P. (2003). Learning to teach in higher education. Routledge.
- [12] Rossouw, J. P. & Niemczyk, E. K. (2019). Drives towards research productivity: international trends. Human rights in diverse education contexts (pp. 283-309). Pretoria: AOSIS.
- [13] Singh, R. (2017). Naac Assessment for higher Education: A boon. International journal of current Research, 9(08), 56798-56800
- [14] Sustainable Development Goal 4. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sustainable_Development_Goal_4
- [15] The Royal Society. Research Culture. <https://royalsociety.org/topics-policy/projects/research-culture/>
- [16] Tierney, W. G. (1997). Organizational socialization in higher education. The Journal of Higher Education, 68(1), 1-16.
- [17] University Grants Commission Report (2019). UGC. Ministry of Higher Education. <https://repository.lahoreschool.edu.pk/xmlui/bitstream/handle/123456789/18919/2019-20.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>
- [18] White, P. J., & Deevy, C. (2020). Designing an Interdisciplinary Research Culture in Higher Education: A Case Study. Springer, 51(4), 499-515. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10780-020-09406-0>
- [19] William, G. T., & Michael, L. (2018). Institutional Culture in Higher Education. Encyclopedia of International Higher Education Systems and Institutions, DOI: [10.1007/978-94-017-9553-1_544-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-9553-1_544-1). <file:///C:/Users/ACER/Desktop/NAAC/TierneyandLanford2018.pdf>
- [20] World economic forum. (Sep 18, 2018). 7 Ways to promote better research culture. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2018/09/7-ways-to-promote-better-research-culture/>
- [21] Yang, B., Bao, S., & Xu, J. (2022). Supervisory styles and graduate student innovation performance: The mediating role of psychological capital and the moderating role of harmonious academic passion. Frontiers in Psychology, 13, 1034216.